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Threads of Identity the Visual Evolution of Pakistan Post

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Abstract

The visual identity of Pakistan Post reflects a remarkable story of transformation that mirrors the country's historical and cultural evolution. Emerging from the legacy of

the British Raj, Pakistan Post inherited both its administrative structure and its early design aesthetics. Over time, this institution gradually reshaped its visual symbols to express a distinct national character. The early stamps and logos carried colonial motifs such as crowns and imperial insignias, representing authority and hierarchy. As Pakistan developed its own national consciousness, these foreign symbols gave way to local elements like the crescent, star, and traditional instruments, reflecting the spirit of independence and cultural pride. This study traces the journey of Pakistan Post's design evolution—from the early Scinde Dawk stamp of 1852 to the modern rebranding of the twenty-first century—highlighting how visual communication became a medium for expressing identity, progress, and nationhood. Through a historical and design-based analysis, this research reveals how graphic design in state institutions functions not only as a tool of communication but also as a reflection of social values, heritage, and collective memory in Pakistan's visual culture.

Key Words: Pakistan Post, GPO, Identity, British Raj, Postal Stamps, Logo, Logos of Pakistan

Introduction

The history of the Pakistan Post Office is deeply rooted in the colonial postal network of the Indian subcontinent, a system that once symbolized imperial communication and later evolved into a national institution of identity and service. From the early nineteenth century, when letters were carried by men on foot under the British Raj, to the modern era of digital and financial services, the post office has remained a constant presence in the social and administrative landscape of South Asia. Its transformation is not only a reflection of technological progress but also a mirror of cultural and political change.

In tracing this evolution, one finds that the story of Pakistan Post is more than a bureaucratic chronicle; it is a narrative of design, symbolism, and national identity. The early stamps of the Scinde District, introduced under Sir Bartle Frere in 1852, carried the insignia of the East India Company, an emblem of authority and order. These stamps, known

as *Scinde Dawk*, marked the beginning of visual communication through postal design in the region. With the establishment of Pakistan in 1947, the inherited colonial postal framework began to adapt to new national aspirations. The British crown and trumpet motifs that once symbolized royal service slowly gave way to indigenous symbols like the crescent and star, echoing the country's Islamic and cultural ethos.

This research explores how the Pakistan Post Office evolved from its colonial origins into a national communication network and how its visual identity through stamps, logos, and emblems, transformed alongside the nation's own search for modernity and self-definition. The post office serves here as both a functional institution and a cultural text: a site where design, politics, and public life intersect. Through an analysis of historical documents, design artifacts, and rebranding initiatives, this study seeks to understand how visual language has played a role in shaping institutional identity, bridging the gap between heritage and contemporary design practices.

Pakistan Post Office

The history of Pakistan Post Office can be traced back to the first half of the nineteenth century in the subcontinent during the period of the British Raj. Back then, the reward (price) and penalty of delivering a letter was decided upon by the 1837 Post Office Act.¹ The year was 1850 when, in Western India, the Sindh region had four major offices in the cities of Shikarpur, Sukkur, Karachi, and Hyderabad. The postal letters from these areas were transported to Bombay by mail men known as *Kasids*.² At that time, stamps were used as a source of identity for the postal department.

The stamps served the same purpose as they did in the British or Roman courts. The first stamp used by the post office in the sub-continent was *Scinde Dawk*. It was designed by *Sir Bartle Frere*, in 1852, in the province of *Scinde*³ (which is now spelt as Sindh) (fig. 7.106).⁴

¹ Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London and New York: John Lane Company, 1921), 31.

² R. Walia, "Celebrating 150 Years of Scinde Dawk Stamps," *The Tribune India*, published on 28 December 2002, <https://www.tribuneindia.com/2002/20021228/windows/main2.htm> (accessed on 03 December 2021).

³ Scinde was a district of India, surrounding by hill tribes, all of whom were robbers and plunderers. An army was ultimately necessary to preserve the peace.

⁴ Clarke, *The Post Office of India, and its Story*, 178.

Figure. 7.106: Scinde Dawk Stamp, Embossed without colour, Designed by Sir Bartle Frere in 1852, Source: Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London: John Lane; New York, John Lane Company, 1921), 178. Stamps from Scinde District were very valuable and consisted of three basic types:

- a) Embossed design without any colour on white paper (fig.5.106)
- b) Embossed in blue colour on white paper (fig. 7.107)
- c) Vermilion wafers that were embossed (fig. 7.108).

Figure. 7.107: Scinde Dawk Stamp, Embossed in Blue colour, Designed by Sir Bartle Frere in 1852, Source: Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London: John Lane; New York, John Lane Company, 1921), 178.

Figure. 7.108: Scinde Dawk Stamp, Embossed on vermillion wafer, Designed by Sir Bartle Frere in 1852, Source: Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London: John Lane; New York, John Lane Company, 1921), 178.

These stamps had a design format based on a heart-shaped symbol divided into three sections and each section bore a letter in it. These letters were 'E', 'I' and 'C' and they stood for East India Company. The stamps had been used since September 1854. Initially, the postal organization in the British Raj was solely used by officials. Later in 1837 a public postal system was established and the production of a variety of stamps was introduced accordingly.⁵ The Court of Directors in London and within the Indian Government held serious discussions on the issue whether these stamps should be mass-produced or not. The former had a desire that they be printed in London. However keeping economy in mind, it was decided that quality stamps could be produced in India. Later on, various stamps were produced, and the public began purchasing them in 1860. Indian postal stamps were printed in a smaller size than the English stamps and had the inscription East India Postage engraved on them. In 1882, *Messrs. De La Rue* designed a stamp that had a comparatively larger size and changed the inscription to Indian Postage.⁶ From that time onwards, various postal stamps were printed, and all were British Series. An example was the Specimen Victorian Issue (fig. 7.109), Specimen Edwardian and Georgian Issue (fig. 7.110). The post office in the British Raj had a great deal of western influence which could be seen reflected in the stamps for decades.

⁵ R. Walia, "Celebrating 150 Years of Scinde Dawk Stamps," *The Tribune India*, printed on Saturday, 28 December 2002, <https://www.tribuneindia.com/2002/20021228/windows/main2.htm> (accessed on 09 December 2021).

⁶ Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London and New York: John Lane Company, 1921), 165.

Rawalpindi has the oldest GPO office which was established in 1876.⁷ By the time of the partition in 1947, Pakistan Post Office came into being. The post office began dealing in both types of services: telegrams and telegraphs.

Figure. 7.109: Postal Stamps from British Raj, Specimen Victorian Issue, Source: Source: Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India and its Story* (London: John Lane; New York, John Lane Company, 1921), 183.

⁷ Aamir Yasin, “Postal Services-Thriving in the Age of Internet,” *The DAWN Newspaper*, published on 16 July 2017, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1345604> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.110: Postal Stamps from British Raj, Specimen Edwardian and Georgian Issues, Source: Source: Geoffrey Clarke, *The Post Office of India, and its Story* (London: John Lane; New York, John Lane Company, 1921), 183. The very first visual identity of Pakistan Post Office carried the influence of the British Raj even though it was manifested after the birth of Pakistan (fig. 7.111).

Figure. 7.111: Pakistan Post Office Logo with british influence, Source: Newsposts, “Pakistan Post to Expand its Network with 15,000 New Outlets”, *Post and Parcel*, last modified on 22 February 2019, <https://postandparcel.info/101479/news/pakistan-post-to-expand-its-network-with-15000-new-outlets/> (accessed on 09 December 2021).

In this logo, the image of a crown can be seen which is Victorian in nature. Also, a musical instrument (trumpet) suggests a call of duty to do something. Basically, it is a sign which represents the telegraphic services, and the crossed arrows depict speed and direction. In 1987, Pakistan Post Office published a stamp in order to celebrate its fortieth anniversary in which an updated logo can be seen (fig. 7.112 and 7.113).

Figure. 7.112: Stamp published on the 40th Anniversary of Pakistan Post Office with updated logo. Source: Wahid Zia, “40 Years of Pakistan Post Office (1947-1987)”, *Pakistan Philatelic Net Club*, last modified on 15 August 2009, <http://paknetmag.blogspot.com/2009/08/40-years-of-pakistan-post-office-1947.html> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.113 (a): Logo of Pakistan Post Office, published on the 40th Anniversary of Pakistan Post Office. Source: Wahid Zia, “40 Years of Pakistan Post Office (1947-1987)”, *Pakistan Philatelic Net Club*, last modified on 15 August 2009, <http://paknetmag.blogspot.com/2009/08/40-years-of-pakistan-post-office-1947.html> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.113 (b): Logo of Pakistan Post Office, re-illustrated by author, re-illustrated in Adobe Illustrator and Photoshop

This visual identity evolved into a traditional emblem design and ultimately abandoned British influence. The crescent moon with a star replaced the crown and as for the trumpet, it was replaced by a local and ethnic musical instrument which looks like a trumpet but is actually known as a *Baja* in the native language. In between these two elements there is a blue coloured banner on which the name Pakistan Post is written in Urdu. The vision of the post office is written on the crescent in Urdu as well. In the 1990s, this emblem was designed, and the name of Pakistan Post was penned beneath the emblem in bold, sans-serif and capital letters in the English language. The distance between the words written on the crescent decreased and the calligraphy became more elegant in its demeanor (fig. 7.114 and 7.115).

Figure. 7.114: Logo of Pakistan Post Office, Updated in 1990s, Picture credit: Tanveer Shehzad, Source: Aamir Yasin, “Postal Services-Thriving in the Age of Internet”, *The DAWN Newspaper*, published on 16 July 2017, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1345604> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.115: Pakistan Post Updated logo, Black and White and Coloured Variation, Designed in 1990s, Source: Staff Reporter, “Pakistan Post Introduces Digital Financial Services”, *The Nation Newspaper*, published on 04 June 2020, <https://nation.com.pk/04-Jun-2020/pakistan-post-introduces-digital-financial-services> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

This logo was used by the post office till 2015 in various newspaper ads and in other official pursuits. However, in this period, the post office also used a novel logo. There was even a time when these two different

designs were used simultaneously. In 2007, Pakistan Post Office launched a brand-new logo as a result of rebranding (fig. 7.116 and 7.117).⁸

Figure. 7.116: Pakistan Post Updated logo, exhibited on the letter boxes, updated in 2007, Source: Fawad Maqsood, “Rs370mn allocated for rebranding 550 Pakistan Post offices”, *Business Recorder*, last modified on 18 May 2018, <https://www.brecorder.com/news/418468/rs370mn-allocated-for-re-branding-550-pakistan-post-offices> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.117: Postal stamp of rebranding, Pakistan Post launched a new logo in 2007 in the result of rebranding, Source: Waheed Rahman, “Pakistan Post Stamps/tickets”, *My Collecting hobbies*, last modified on 3 September 2011, <http://collectinghobbies.blogspot.com/2011/09/pakistan-post-stampstickets.html> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

The symbol in this logo has been completely transformed and the depiction of joining hands is prominent although the name is the same as in the previous logo. This logo was extant till 2016 (fig. 7.118).

⁸ Waheed Rahman, “Pakistan Post Stamps/Tickets,” *My Collecting Hobbies*, last modified on 3 September 2011, <http://collectinghobbies.blogspot.com/2011/09/pakistan-post-stampstickets.html> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Figure. 7.118: Display of Old logo in a ceremony, held in 2015, Source: Correspondent, “Pakistan Post Stops Opening New Accounts”, *The Express Tribune*, published on 14 November 2020, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2272262/pakistan-post-stops-opening-new-accounts> (accessed on 10 December 2021).

Towards the end of 2015, Pakistan Post Office decided to completely computerize its data and launch new services online to enhance its services and facilitate its consumers. As a result, consumer loyalty skyrocketed. To launch the new services, a fresh visual identity was obviously required for the post office. With the Postal Amendments Agenda, the Government of Pakistan upgraded its offices by means of rebranding and changed the look of the logo to rejuvenate the brand image.⁹ The new logo of Pakistan Post fulfilled all the requirements of contemporary logo design (fig. 7.119 and 7.120).

⁹ News Desk, “Pakistan Post to Computerize GPOs Record,” NEWS Pakistan, last modified on 25 May 2018, <https://newspakistan.tv/pakistan-post-to-computerize-gpos-record/> (accessed on 13 December 2021).

Figure. 7.119: Rebranded logo of Pakistan Post, launched in 2015, Source: Newa Desk, “Pakistan Post to Computerize GPOs Record”, *NEWS Pakistan*, last modified on 25 May 2018, <https://newspakistan.tv/pakistan-post-to-computerize-gpos-record/> (accessed on 13 December 2021).

Figure. 7.120: Rebranding of letterbox with updated logo of Pakistan Post, launched in 2015, Picture Credit: Author.

The symbol in the logo design was a representation of a paper airplane in simplified form, and it is facing a downwards direction. The name "Post Office" was written in the previously designed font style, and the name "Pakistan Post" is also written in the Urdu language.

Conclusion

The visual journey of Pakistan Post stands as more than a record of institutional design; it reflects the nation's evolving identity and sense of self. From the colonial imagery of the British Raj to the emergence of a distinctly Pakistani aesthetic, every logo, emblem, and stamp tells a story of transformation. The gradual shift from imperial crowns to crescents and

stars, and from foreign symbols to indigenous motifs, represents more than graphic change, it mirrors a cultural reawakening. Pakistan Post has continued to adapt with technological progress, balancing heritage with modern communication needs. This evolution shows how design can serve as a silent but powerful storyteller, carrying the values, aspirations, and collective memory of a nation. Ultimately, the history of Pakistan Post's visual identity illustrates how design, when grounded in cultural context, becomes a living expression of national pride and creative continuity.

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